

Modern Diagnostics of the Impact of Microorganisms and Infectious Complications in Surgery

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Abstract: The problem of preventing postoperative purulent complications in abdominal surgery remains relevant to this day. This is mainly due to the increase in the number of complex operations using modern technologies, the increase in the volume and duration of surgical interventions, increased tissue damage and blood loss, which contributes to the development of postoperative infectious complications, primarily wound infection. Treatment of wound infection requires additional costs and significantly increases the patient's stay in the hospital.

Keywords: Postoperative rehabilitation, indexation, pathological focus, antibacterial therapy.

Introduction

Despite the improvement of surgical techniques and the introduction of a system of preventive measures, the incidence of postoperative wound infection in abdominal operations remains high. Thus, the number of postoperative purulent complications in planned abdominal operations is 6-8%; Moreover, if purulent complications develop in 0.8-2% of cases during "clean" operations, then in "contaminated" or dirty operations the number of purulent wounds increases to 20% [39].

The frequency of suppuration of postoperative wounds in the abdominal organs is determined by the nature of the disease, the degree of trauma of the surgical intervention, and the likelihood of microbial infection of the surgical wound.

The incidence of postoperative purulent complications when performing minimally traumatic laparoscopic cholecystectomy is 0.6–6% [7,17], and with laparotomic cholecystectomy this figure increases to 5–26% [4,5].

Selective proximal vagotomy (SPV) operations also account for a small percentage (1.8%) of postoperative purulent-inflammatory complications [2].

There is an increased incidence of wound suppurative complications after operations involving the opening of hollow organs. In addition, the incidence of postoperative infectious complications during gastric resection is significantly increased and ranges from 4 to 26% [11,8].

The frequency of purulent complications remains high in liver surgery - 27-58% [1,6,8,2] and in pancreatic surgery - 40-70% [17,29,30,4,2].

The highest number of postoperative purulent-septic complications (68%) is observed during surgical interventions on the colon [36]. The most severe complication in abdominal surgery is peritonitis, the incidence of which ranges from 3 to 70%, and the mortality rate reaches 20% [4,5].

Research Methods and Materials: According to CDC's National Nosocomial Infection Surveillance (NNIS) reports, surgical site infections (SSIs) are the third most commonly reported nosocomial infections, accounting for 14–16% of all hospital-acquired infections [64]. From 1986 to 1996, hospitals that maintained SSI surveillance in the NNIS system reported 15,523 SSIs after 593,344 surgeries. Of these total SSIs, two-thirds involved organs or spaces located in the incision area and one-third involved surgical access sites [64]. The occurrence of an SSI prolongs a patient's hospital stay by 10 days and increases the cost of hospitalization by \$2000 [56,57]. Despite significant advances in the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of surgical site infection, its occurrence in the United States approximately doubles hospitalization costs [72].

While the question of the appropriateness of prophylactic antibiotic use in abdominal surgery has been widely debated in the past, most researchers have now concluded that this approach is necessary and valuable [9,13,21,24,27,28,34,37,39,42,51,63,68]. Today, antibacterial prophylaxis of postoperative infections is a routine part of surgical practice in clean contaminated operations, as well as in some clean procedures [70].

Prophylactic use of antimicrobial drugs in surgery should be understood as the prevention of postoperative infectious complications by preoperative (perioperative) administration of antimicrobial agents to the operated organ and surgical wound, which are suspected pathogens of the flora. Prophylactic use of antibiotics leads to a reduction in economic costs associated with the development of postoperative suppuration, mortality, and infection. At the same time, antibiotic prophylaxis of wound infection in planned abdominal surgery has not yet found clear answers to many questions.

In recent years, approaches to a standard definition of SSI have been reported in the literature [20,67,67,73], which seems to be possible when comparing infectious complications of any anatomical part of the body opened or manipulated during surgery (Tables 1 and 2) and may serve as a criterion for the effectiveness of the use of perioperative antimicrobial drugs.

It should be noted that when hospitalized, the patient inevitably encounters hospital strains. In addition, as the duration of stay in a medical institution increases, the likelihood of the patient replacing his own microflora with hospital microflora increases. In this regard, infectious processes developing in hospitalized patients can be caused by both community and hospital microflora [22].

According to data from the NNIS (USA) and local researchers, the prevalence of pathogens isolated during SSI has not changed significantly over the past decade, although these rates vary greatly between different surgical clinics [21]

The most frequently isolated pathogens remain: Staphylococcus aureus, coagulase-negative staphylococci, Enterococcus spp. and Escherichia coli. Antimicrobial-resistant pathogens such as methicillin-resistant S. aureus (MRSA) and Candida albicans[3,10,]

Microbial contamination of the surgical wound is inevitable even with full compliance with the rules of asepsis and antisepsis, and at the end of the operation, in 80-90% of cases, the wounds are seeded with various microflora, most often staphylococci [44].

Research results: Biver A. showed in a large clinical sample that although wounds are contaminated at the end of surgery in 80-90% of cases, purulent complications develop in 2-30% of cases [52]. This is apparently explained by the fact that the number of microbes in the surgical wound must be at least 10^5 for SSI to develop [22,38,69].

At the same time, Davydovsky IV [15,16] emphasized that for the development of infection in a wound, not only the type of pathogen, but also the state of the macroorganism, as well as the functional state of the damaged tissues, are of decisive importance. Therefore, the author emphasized that the main motto of surgeons should be "not the fight against bacteria in the wound, but the fight for the anatomical purity of the wound."

It is important to note that monitoring primary and "secondary" risk factors for the development of SSI in the preoperative and postoperative periods is useful for two reasons:

- they provide the possibility of stratification by type of operation, making epidemiological surveillance data more understandable;
- knowledge of risk factors before specific operations allows targeted measures to be taken to prevent infection [65].

However, the effectiveness of antibacterial protection can be more accurately assessed by assessing the level of risk of developing infectious complications using a scoring system [2].

It is known that the widespread use of broad-spectrum antibiotics affects the bacterial flora, which leads to the selection of a resistant population from the focus of infection or from the endogenous microflora of the patient. In case of violation of sanitary and hygienic rules in the surgical department, resistant strains of

microorganisms can be transmitted from patient to patient through hands and the environment. It is known that when a patient is in a surgical hospital for 48 hours, his biological econych (skin, mucous membranes of the respiratory tract and gastrointestinal tract) is replenished with hospital strains of microorganisms.

Studies conducted in recent years have shown that the normal human microflora is an open biocenosis, consisting of obligate (autochthonous, resident) and transient (adventitious) microorganisms, in dynamic equilibrium with the host organism and its environment. In most cases, the source of invasion in endogenous infections is the lumen of the digestive tract and its mucous membranes - the habitat of automicroflora.

It is known that there are more than 300 species of microorganisms in the oral cavity. Their number in saliva can reach 10^9 CFU / ml. The stomach is usually contaminated with microorganisms that enter the oral cavity with food and saliva. The number of microorganisms is 10^3 CFU / ml. In the duodenum, jejunum and upper ileum it is less than 10^4 CFU / ml. In the large intestine there are more than 400 species of microorganisms. Their number reaches 10^{12-14} CFU / ml. They are represented by strict and facultative anaerobes, residual microflora and various representatives of the Enterobacteriaceae family.

The gastrointestinal tract has always been considered an organ of nutrient absorption that is impaired under extreme conditions [33]. However, studies conducted over the past 20 years have shown that one source of endogenous infection is microbial translocation [25,58–60].

Translocation of microorganisms is understood as the movement of viable bacteria and their toxins through the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract to extraintestinal areas of the macroorganism: mesenteric lymph nodes, liver, spleen, and systemic bloodstream. The phenomenon of translocation of bacteria and their toxins from the gastrointestinal tract to the internal environment of the body is considered one of the universal infectious mechanisms of the formation of endogenous intoxication syndrome during excessive exposure to the organism.

The above justifies the search for objective criteria, the solution of which will allow for the objective use of effective methods for the prevention of postoperative purulent complications in the preoperative, intraoperative and postoperative periods.

One of the least studied aspects of preventing these complications is the rational use of antibacterial drugs. It should be noted that, despite the importance of this area in surgery, in no case should the problem of postoperative suppuration be reduced solely by the search for an optimal antibiotic prophylaxis regimen. This approach ignores the most important principles of suppuration prevention.

The feasibility of antibiotic prophylaxis in elective abdominal surgery is currently undisputed, and the literature discusses the optimal antibiotic regimen for achieving maximum clinical efficacy; Hell K. argues that the prophylactic use of antibiotics during surgical interventions has saved more lives over the past 20 years than any other improvement in this area [37].

When determining the tactics for using antibiotics for preventive purposes, the following questions should be answered correctly:

1. What should guidelines for antibiotic prophylaxis identify?
2. When is it appropriate to start antibiotic prophylaxis?
3. What is the optimal duration of prophylactic antibiotic use?
4. What medications and in what doses should be used for preventive purposes?
5. Which route of administration of antibiotics should be considered optimal?

The correct answer to these questions determines the rational tactics of antibiotic prophylaxis. A simple and reliable criterion for determining the indications for the use of antibiotics for prophylactic purposes is the division of operations into 4 groups or classes according to the degree of potential contamination (Table 4). This classification is a working scheme, based on the degree of microbial contamination of the surgical field, as well as the type of “cleanliness” of the surgical intervention, the absence of antimicrobial drugs for prophylaxis or their use before surgery, and the risk of developing bacterial complications [13,30].

The optimal time to start antibiotic prophylaxis is to administer the first dose of the drug before anesthesia, so that the surgical intervention is performed against the background of maximum antibiotic concentrations in the blood and tissues, which are maintained throughout the entire period of surgical intervention.

The main mistake in timing the first dose of antibiotics is to start the prophylactic course postoperatively, since during surgery, when a “good nutrient environment” is present, the microflora entering the wound multiplies, and the use of antibiotics becomes ineffective and inappropriate [27].

It was found that if antibacterial therapy is started 2 hours before the incision, postoperative infection develops in 3.8% of cases, compared with 0.5% when antibiotics are administered 1 hour before the start of the operation. If antibiotics are used after the start of the operation, the frequency of infection begins to increase and reaches 5% 8-9 hours after the incision, and the probability of infection is higher if antibiotic prophylaxis is used after the start of the operation [55].

Pharmacokinetic studies of cephalosporins show that after a single intravenous injection of drugs before surgery during laparoscopic cholecystectomy, their maximum concentration in the blood is determined after 15 minutes. Perioperative use of ofloxacin for prophylactic purposes in focal lesions of the liver (hemangioma, adenocarcinoma, echinococcus) has shown that with the first intravenous dose of 200 mg of ofloxacin 15 minutes before the start of the operation, sufficient therapeutic concentrations of the drug are created in the blood, tissues, and liver [404]. The use of metronidazole (Metrogil) as an antianaerobic drug allows not only to affect anaerobic flora, but also enhances the effect of cephalosporins on aerobic bacteria. This creates conditions for exposure to the entire spectrum of pathogens that cause intraoperative infections. The widespread use of Metrogil is due to the high efficacy of the drug against anaerobes, good tolerability, and the absence of bacterial resistance to it. The drug is effective against pathogens resistant to other anaerobic drugs. The initial dose of the drug for intravenous administration is 15 mg / kg. The maximum daily dose is 4 g.

There is no consensus on the timing of perioperative antibiotics in abdominal cavity surgery and this is a matter of debate. There are several time intervals for the duration of antibiotic administration in the postoperative period. According to MI. Kuzina et al. [17], in clean operations, a single administration of antibiotics before anesthesia is used. In conditionally clean operations, if there are special indications - for use in clean operations, an ultra-short course (within 24 hours) with mandatory pre-anesthetic administration is recommended. Short-term prophylaxis (48-72 hours) is often used in contaminated operations and in some cases in relatively clean ones. Long-term antibiotic prophylaxis (more than 3 days) is used for "contaminated" and "dirty" operations.

Antibiotic prophylaxis for no more than 24 hours is considered optimal by some authors. When the time interval for prescribing antibiotics is extended, it is considered antimicrobial therapy [61,66].

According to MI. Kuzina et al. [28], the optimal period for the prophylactic use of antibiotics in abdominal operations is 48-72 hours with mandatory pre-anesthetic administration of the drug. However, it is not excluded that this period may be extended, determined by the specific clinical situation.

The choice of antimicrobial drug is important for preventive purposes. The indications are based on the nature of the microflora growing in the organ being operated on, as well as on complete information about the hospital strains of this hospital. Treatment in such conditions is the selection of broad-spectrum antibiotics that effectively affect the potential pathogen. One of the important conditions when choosing an antibiotic is to ensure its sufficient concentration in the blood and tissues of the organ being operated on for the entire period of surgical intervention. The antibiotic should have minimal toxicity. The drug should be optimal in terms of cost/effectiveness.

The most important principle for prescribing an antimicrobial agent is to know whether the proposed surgical site will provide access to areas of the body that are reliably colonized by obligate anaerobes (*Bacteroides* spp.). If the presence of anaerobic microflora is suspected, for example, during colon, distal ileum, or appendectomy operations, antibacterial agents effective against *Bacteroides* spp. should be used. [18]

The main condition for choosing the dose of the antibiotic should be to ensure adequate concentration in the blood and tissues. The goal should be to achieve a concentration 2-3 times higher than the MIC for the likely pathogen. The choice of the method of administration of antibiotics is made depending on the clinical situation. Intravenous administration provides a rapid creation of high concentrations of the drug in the blood and tissues.

At the same time, when administered intramuscularly, antibiotics are retained in the tissues for longer, creating a depot for their gradual release into the bloodstream.

Conclusion: In connection with the above, the question naturally arises as to which antimicrobial drugs should be used for prophylaxis. Currently, there are no single schemes. No antibiotic can prevent all types of surgical infections. Any scheme of antibiotic prophylaxis may be ineffective if the risk factors for the development of postoperative purulent complications, as well as the microbiological landscape of the hospital flora, which is individual for each surgical clinic, are not taken into account. It is clear that it would be useful to develop a formula for the use of antimicrobial drugs for each surgical clinic.

Analysis of the results of a study conducted on more than 1,500 patients made it possible to note that suppuration occurred in 1.4% of cases in clean operations without the use of antibiotics, and suppuration was not observed after a single dose of the drug in operations in this group.

The number of suppurations in conditionally clean operations with the use of antibiotics was 3.3% compared to 10.1% without antibiotics.

In "contaminated" operations, the rate of suppuration with the use of antibiotics for prophylaxis is observed in 7.3% of patients, compared to 21.8% without antibiotic prophylaxis.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the use of antibiotics for prophylactic purposes in abdominal surgery is an important component in improving surgical outcomes and reducing the length of stay of patients in the surgical clinic.

The main principle of antibiotic prophylaxis is the perioperative use of a broad-spectrum drug in adequate doses. When choosing an antimicrobial drug, it is necessary to take into account not only the patient's condition, but also surgical invasiveness factors.

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